

Halogenation of Copper(II) Complexes Containing Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Cupric complexes having the formula CuL_2X_2 were reacted with chlorine and bromine and several crystalline complexes of the type $[\text{LH}]_2[\text{CuX}_4]$ where L is quinoline, isoquinoline, γ -picoline and 4-cyanopyridine and X is Cl^- or Br^- and $[\text{LH}]_2[\text{CuX}_2\text{Y}_2]$ where X is Cl^- and Y is Br^- were isolated. All these compounds were characterised on the basis of their analyses, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infra-red and electronic spectral data.

Halogenation reaction of several transition metal complexes of the type ML_2X_2 , where M is a divalent metal like zinc, nickel and manganese, L is a nitrogen donor ligand and X is Cl^- or Br^- were reported earlier^{1,2,3,9}. Several tetra-, penta- and hexa-coordinated anionic complexes were reported for divalent nickel and zinc. It was thought worthwhile to extend the investigation to the case of cupric complexes. A number of electrolytic complexes having the formulae $[\text{LH}]_2[\text{CuX}_4]$ and $[\text{LH}]_2[\text{CuX}_2\text{Y}_2]$ where L is quinoline, isoquinoline, γ -picoline and 4-cyanopyridine, X is chloride or bromide and Y is bromide are reported in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the materials used were of A.R. grade. CuL_2X_2 type of complexes were prepared by previously reported methods^{4,5,6}.

Chlorination : To an ethanolic suspension of a CuL_2Cl_2 complex, pure and dry chlorine gas was passed slowly till a clear solution was obtained with an exothermic reaction. The solution was cooled overnight when yellow or orange-yellow compound separated out. Chlorination of CuL_2Br_2 complexes resulted in the complete replacement of bromine by chlorine.

Bromination : Ethanolic suspensions of CuL_2Cl_2 and CuL_2Br_2 complexes were treated separately with liquid bromine dropwise and the mixture shaken till a clear solution was obtained with exothermic reaction. On cooling overnight, dark violet crystalline compounds separated out. The compounds were suction filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. Halogenation reaction did not succeed in CHCl_3 and CCl_4 media probably due to the absence of a solvolytic mechanism.

Purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating metal and halogen by standard methods. Conductance was measured in acetone medium ($M/1000$ solution) using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge and dip type cell. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on solid specimens using Gouy method. I.R. spectra were recorded on

TABLE I
Analyses, melting point, conductance and magnetic susceptibility data of copper(II) complexes

Compound	Colour and Form*	M.P. (°C)	Λ_M (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	% Copper		% Chlorine		% Bromine	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
$[QH]_2 [CuCl]$	Orange Yellow	172	226.5	1.99	13.44	13.66	30.30	30.50	—	—
$[QH]_2 [CuCl_2Br_2]$	Dark Violet	155	181.0	1.83	11.33	11.47	12.68	12.81	28.80	28.83
$[QH]_2 [CuBr_4]$	Dark Violet	152	172.8	1.79	9.96	9.88	—	—	49.58	49.69
$[IQH]_2 [CuCl_4]$	Orange Yellow	180	219.2	1.91	13.35	13.66	30.36	30.50	—	—
$[IQH]_2 [CuCl_2Br_2]$	Dark Violet	142	202.7	1.89	11.25	11.47	12.56	12.81	28.67	28.83
$[IQH]_2 [CuBr_4]$	Dark Violet	130	172.2	1.82	9.65	9.88	—	—	49.46	49.69
$[\gamma\text{-Pic.H}]_2 [CuCl_4]$	Yellow	185	206.3	1.90	15.96	16.14	35.85	36.06	—	—
$[\gamma\text{-Pic.H}]_2 [CuCl_2Br_2]$	Dark Violet	165	195.4	1.75	12.94	13.17	14.56	14.72	32.98	33.12
$[\gamma\text{-Pic.H}]_2 [CuBr_4]$	Dark Violet	160	162.1	1.71	10.95	11.13	—	—	55.72	55.94
$[4\text{-CN.Py.H}]_2 [CuCl_4]$	Yellow	152	174.2	2.02	15.11	15.30	33.83	34.18	—	—
$[4\text{-CN.Py.H}]_2 [CuCl_2Br_2]$	Dark Green	158	186.3	1.86	12.36	12.60	13.85	14.08	31.36	31.69
$[4\text{-CN.Py.H}]_2 [CuBr_4]$	Dark Violet	167	166.4	1.86	10.56	10.71	—	—	53.64	53.88

* All the compounds are crystalline.

Q = Quinoline, IQ = Iso-Quinoline, γ -Pic. = γ -picoline, 4-CN.Py = 4-Cyano-pyridine.

hexachlorobutadiene mulls using a Unicam SP-200 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra in the visible range were recorded with *M*/100 acetone solutions using Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer. All the relevant analytical, conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are recorded in table 1. The infra-red and electronic spectral data are recorded in table 2.

TABLE 2

Infra-red (N-H stretching frequencies) and visible spectral data of Copper(II) complexes

Compound	$\nu(\text{N-H}), \text{cm}^{-1}$	$\nu_{\text{max}}, \text{cm}^{-1} (\epsilon)$
$[\text{QH}]_2 [\text{CuCl}_4]$	3040 br	20,500(1209)s, 13,200(70)br
$[\text{IQH}]_2 [\text{CuCl}_4]$	2920 br	20,800(960)s, 13,400(107)br
	3060 br	
$(\gamma\text{-Pic-H})_2 [\text{CuCl}_4]$	2880 s	20600(1902)s, 13,400(119)br
	2940 s	
	3080 s	
$[4\text{-CN.Py.H}]_2 [\text{CuCl}_4]$	2965 s	20,600(1299)s, 13,400(12)br
	3080 s	
$[\text{QH}]_2 [\text{CuCl}_2\text{Br}_2]$	2890 m	17500(33)br
	3020 m	
$[\text{IQH}]_2 [\text{CuCl}_2\text{Br}_2]$	3040 br	17800(17)br
$[\gamma\text{-Pic.H}]_2 [\text{CuCl}_2\text{Br}_2]$	2960 s	17,600(12)br
	3090 m	
$[4\text{-CN.Py.H}]_2 [\text{CuCl}_2\text{Br}_2]$	2855 m	17,600(19)br
	3020 s	
	3080 s	
$[\text{QH}]_2 [\text{CuBr}_4]$	3040 br	17600(80)br
$[\text{IQH}]_2 [\text{CuBr}_4]$	3090 br	17,400(104)br
$[\gamma\text{-Pic.H}]_2 [\text{CuBr}_4]$	3000 s	17,600(40)br
	3120 m	
$[4\text{ CN.Py.H}]_2 [\text{CuBr}_4]$	2830 s	17,600(49)br
	2990 br	

s—sharp, m—medium, br—broad.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is well known that if copper(II) forms a six co-ordinated complex, this will have distorted octahedral configuration due to Jahn-Teller effect. More usually it forms four-co-ordinated complexes which are either square planar or tetrahedral.

When chlorine gas was passed into the suspension of CuL_2X_2 complexes in ethanol, it may react in two ways : (1) Chlorine may get into the pyridine or quinoline ring or (2) chlorine may react with hydrogen of ethanol to form HCl which subsequently reacts with bonded ligand base forming quaternary halides. In the present case substitution in the

pyridine ring has not taken place. If it were so, the formula would have been $[\text{Cu}(\text{py}.\text{Cl})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and the analysis of the compound would have indicated the presence of only two halogen atoms since ring halogen can not be estimated by dil. HNO_3 treatment, but requires prior fusion. Further, such a compound would be a non-electrolyte.

The compounds obtained are yellow, orange-yellow or dark violet crystalline solids and are fairly soluble in acetone in which medium they are 2 : 1 electrolytes, the molar conductance values (Λ_M) being more than 150 mhos (table 1). The dark violet compounds give deep green solutions in acetone which undergo colour change on heating, on dilution or on keeping for a day or two probably due to solvolysis. Infra-red spectra (table 2) indicate the presence of N-H stretching frequency in the 3000 cm^{-1} region, the interference of Nujol absorption in this region is avoided by using hexachlorobutadiene as the mulling agent. A number of four-co-ordinated tetrahalo complexes of copper(II) have been reported^{7,8} in the literature. They were prepared by the reaction of copper halides and quaternary halides. The compounds now reported are some more examples of this category. However, in the present work, the method of preparation is different since the quaternary halide was obtained *in situ* from the bonded ligand base. When this work was in progress, Mundie and Nuttal⁹ reported $[\text{PyH}]_2[\text{MX}_4]$ type of complexes where M is Zn(II) and Ni(II) by the reaction of halogen with bispyridine metal halides, a method similar to our present method. They recorded the infra-red spectra of Nujol mulls and reported the bands due to N-H stretching frequency. We could not similarly distinguish from the spectra since the mulling agent—Nujol also absorbs heavily in the same region. To avoid this interference, we recorded the spectra on hexachlorobutadiene mulls and could clearly distinguish the bands due to N-H stretching frequencies, since the mulling agent does not adsorb in this region.

Magnetic measurements indicated the complexes to be paramagnetic (μ_{eff} values ranging between 1.75 and 2.02 B.M.) as expected for complexes of cupric ion with d^9 configuration.

The absorption bands noticed in the electronic spectra are recorded in table 2. From the spectra, the complexes can be classified into two categories. The first category of compounds containing $[\text{CuCl}_2\text{Br}_2]^-$ and $[\text{CuBr}_4]^-$ ions show a single band in the $17,400\text{--}17,800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region indicative of a square configuration¹⁰⁻¹³. The second category of complexes containing $[\text{CuCl}_4]^-$ ions exhibit a broad band in the $13000\text{--}13400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region and a sharp intense band in the $20500\text{--}20800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. The extinction coefficients, ϵ , are indicated in parenthesis (table 2). From the spectra and crystal structure determination, both planar and distorted tetrahedral stereo-chemistry have been suggested^{9,14,15} for compounds containing $[\text{CuCl}_4]^-$ ions. For a truly tetrahedral copper(II) complex crystal field theory predicts one transition ${}^2T_2 \rightarrow 2E$. But Sacconi and Ciampolini¹⁶ studied the electronic spectra of a salicylate-deneaminato-copper (II) complex and suggested that the flattening of the tetrahedron results in the splitting of both the ground and excited levels, so that four transitions are expected in the crystal field region. A truly tetrahedral compound should exhibit¹⁰ one broad band below $10,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, but they obtained bands at 8,500; 13,500 and $21,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and predicted a pseudo-tetrahedral configuration for their compound. In the spectra of chloro complexes, we could not record the band below $10,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as the spectra

were studied only upto $10,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, but obtained the two other bands near the same regions reported by Sacconi *et al.* Hence it is expected that the tetrachloro complexes have a pseudotetrahedral configuration. This is also in confirmity with the more recent observation¹⁷ that tetra alkyl ammonium tetrachloro cuprates contain discrete distorted tetrahedral CuCl_4^{-2} ions.

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